

THE USE OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF CHOLANGIOGENIC LIVER ABSCESES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11107335>

Abstract.

According to summary data, the incidence of liver abscesses varies from 8 to 15 cases per 100,000 inhabitants per year, and the mortality rate ranges from 5 to 26%. The article presents the results of 29 clinical observations of patients with cholangiogenic liver abscesses. The possibilities of complex and effective use of modern minimally invasive surgical treatment of patients with this pathology are shown. Separate drainage of the biliary tree and liver abscess, first, the biliary tract was drained. It is the earliest possible drainage that allows you to achieve a positive outcome of treatment, and, in particular, allows you to quickly choose a rational antibacterial therapy. This approach is also of great importance in preparing patients in serious condition for further surgical correction.

Keywords: liver abscess, bacterial abscesses minimally invasive techniques, antibacterial therapy.

Introduction.

According to summary data, the incidence of liver abscesses varies from 8 to 15 cases per 100,000 inhabitants per year, and the mortality rate ranges from 5 to 26%. The formation of purulent foci in the liver is accompanied by severe complications such as liver failure and cholangiogenic sepsis [1].

Bacterial abscesses remain one of the most difficult complications in surgical hepatology [2]. Traditionally used in their surgical treatment, various methods of intra- and extraperitoneal accesses are quite traumatic and, often, insufficiently adequate. This is especially true in cases with multiple abscesses, as well as with the development of sepsis [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The widespread introduction of minimally invasive techniques in the form of interventions under the control of ultrasound diagnostics (ultrasound), endoscopy and laparoscopy has made it possible to qualitatively improve the results of treatment of this complex category of patients [8].

Currently, the most common method of treating liver abscesses is percutaneous puncture and drainage of the abscess. In some studies, the effectiveness has been shown at the level of 96 % when using only the puncture

method [9].

In addition to supporters of minimally invasive percutaneous methods, there are also followers of open drainage of abscesses, mainly in multiple liver lesions [10, 11, 12].

The advantages of minimally invasive methods of treating abscesses under ultrasound control are due to their low traumatism, relative simplicity, lack of risk of general anesthesia, reduced hospitalization time, and allow for better results at lower cost [13, 14, 15].

The aim of the study was to improve the surgical treatment of patients with cholangiogenic liver abscesses using a comprehensive mini-invasive treatment.

Materials and methods of research. The presented study presents the results of treatment of 29 patients with liver abscesses of biliary etiology who were treated in the department of purulent surgery and surgical complications of diabetes mellitus at the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy from 2016 to 2023. All 29 patients underwent mini-invasive percutaneous drainage of liver abscesses and puncture of the common femoral artery according to Seldinger and a special microcatheter is installed into their own liver artery (a. hepatica propria). Among them were 22 (76%) women and 7 (24%) men aged 28 to 69 years. Among 29 patients with biliary liver abscesses treated with minimally invasive methods, 21 (72.4%) had abscesses of the right lobe of the liver, 7 (24%) had abscesses of the left lobe of the liver, 1 (3.4%) had abscesses of both the right and left lobes of the liver. Single abscesses were detected in 19 (65.5%) patients, and in 10 (34.4%) - 2 or more abscesses (multiple). Liver abscesses up to 7 cm in size were detected in 18 patients, more than 7 cm in 11 patients.

The distribution of patients according to the cause of biliary pathology and the occurrence of cholangitis in 20 patients is choledocholithiasis (in 9 cases in combination with acute cholecystitis, in 5 - with a history of cholecystectomy), in 4 - strictures of the biliary tract, in 5 - tumor obturations of hepaticocholedochus.

The results of the treatment. According to the results of treatment of the presented group of patients with cholangiogenic liver abscesses, we consider it necessary to drain the biliary tract and liver abscesses as early as possible from the moment of admission of the patient to the surgical hospital, simultaneously or with a short time interval between them (1-2 days).

Usually, patients complained of body temperature and chills, in the vast majority of cases there was mechanical jaundice and tension of the abdominal wall in the upper right quadrant of the abdomen. Clinical manifestations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Clinical manifestations in patients with biliary liver abscesses

Clinical manifestations	Number of patients	%
Fever, chills	29	100,0
The abdomen pain	28	96,5
Mechanical jaundice	25	86,2
Vomiting	20	68,9
Tension of the abdominal wall in the upper right quadrant of the abdomen	27	91,3
Hepatomegaly	11	37,9

Evaluation of the results of treatment, drainage of the biliary tract and abscess cavity was carried out using ultrasound, analysis of the dynamics of laboratory parameters, as well as the presence of complications and mortality.

Among the patients operated with the use of minimally invasive technologies, 2 complications occurred (6.8%): in 1 patient - bile discharge (100-200 ml per day), in 1 - reactive pleurisy (which, most likely, was a direct complication of liver abscess). There were no fatalities.

Conclusions.

1. Separate drainage of the biliary tree and liver abscess, first, the biliary tract was drained. It is the earliest possible drainage that allows you to achieve a positive outcome of treatment, and, in particular, allows you to quickly choose a rational antibacterial therapy. This approach is also of great importance in preparing patients in serious condition for further surgical correction.

2. The use of minimally invasive techniques in the treatment of liver abscesses of biliary origin in combination with long-term intra-arterial catheter therapy is highly effective and in the future requires a more detailed approach to this method.

3. Percutaneous drainage of liver abscess, percutaneous and endoscopic transpapillary drainage of the biliary tract are complementary components of

minimally invasive surgical intervention in the treatment of liver abscesses of biliary origin.

References:

1. Lubbert C., Wiegand J., Karlas T. Therapy of liver abscesses // *Visceral Medicine*. 2014. Vol. 30, № 5. P. 334-341.
2. Корымасов Е.А. Эффективность малоинвазивных пункционно-дренажных вмешательств в лечении панкреонекроза / Е.А. Корымасов, А.М. Кричмар, Р.М. Джарар // *Казан. Мед. Журнал*. - 2013. - №1. - С.1-6.
3. Meyers W.C. Pyogenic and amebic liver abscess / W.C. Meyers, R.D. Kim // *Sabiston Textbook of Surgery*. - 16th ed. - 2001. - P. 1043-1055.
4. Рузибаев Р.Ю., Курьязов Б.Н., Сапаев Д.Ш., Якубов Ф.Р., Рузматов П.Ю., & Бабаджанов А.Р. (2019). Современная оценка проблем диагностики и хирургического лечения эхинококкоза. *Вестник Национального медико-хирургического Центра им. Н. И. Пирогова*, 14 (1), 134-139.
5. Babadzhanov, A. R., Babadzhanov, K. B., Matmurotov, K. J., Sh, Y. S., & Yokubov, I. Y. (2023). Application of Combined Laser Irradiation in Postoperative Period in Patients with Complicated Hepatic Echinococcosis. *Экономика и социум*, (7 (110)), 66-70.
6. Курьязов, Б. Н., Бабаджанов, А. Р., Рузматов, П. Ю., & Бабаджанов, К. Б. (2024). Эффективность использования минилапаротомного доступа в хирургическом лечении больных желчнокаменной болезнью. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(2), 373-381.
7. Рузматов, П. Ю., Матмуратов, К. Ж., Бабаджанов, А. Р., Каримов, Р. Х., & Рузметов, Б. А. (2024). Особенности выполнения реконструктивных вмешательств у больных синдромом диабетической стопы. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(3), 96-112.
8. Толстиков А.П. Выбор метода хирургического лечения больных с бактериальными абсцессами печени / А.П. Толстиков // *Казан. Мед. Журнал*. - 2012. - №2. - С. 265-269.
9. Cohen, J. L. Liver Abscess : The need for complete gastrointestinal evaluation / J. L. Cohen, V. F. Martin, R. L. Rossi, D. J. Jr. Schoetz // *Arch. Surg*. - 1989. - Vol. 124, № 5. - P. 561-564.
10. Beregi, A. Ultrasonographic detection of abdominal abscess in two guinea pigs / A. Beregi, S. Zorn, V. Molnar, F. Biro // *Acta Vet. Hung*. - 2000. - Vol. 48, № 3. - P. 271-276.

11. Рузибаев, Р. Ю., Курьязов, Б. Н., Сапаев, Д. Ш., & Якубов, Ф. Р. Рузматов П. Ю., & Бабаджанов АР (2019). Современная оценка проблем диагностики и хирургического лечения эхинококкоза. Вестник Национального медико-хирургического Центра им. НИ Пирогова, 14(1), 134-139.
12. Sapaev DS, Yakubov FR, Yakhshiboev SS. Evaluation of the factors influencing the choice of laparoscopic echinococsectomy in liver echinococcosis (LE) and its impact on postoperative outcomes. *Exp Parasitol.* 2023 May;248:108495. doi: 10.1016/j.exppara.2023.108495. Epub 2023 Mar 5. PMID: 36871791.
13. Сапаев Д.Ш., Рузибаев Р.Ю., Курьязов Б.Н. Пятилетний опыт современных операций в лечении эхинококкоза печени // Профилактическая и клиническая медицина. –2017. –№4 (65). –С. 74–78.
14. Лебедев, М.С. Применение внутриполостной лазертерапии в хирургии моделированных абсцессов / М. С. Лебедев, А. И. Урусова, Д. А. Андреев // Бюллетень медицинских Интернет-конференций. - 2015. - Т. 5, №4. -С. 255-256.
15. Sapaev D.S., Yakubov F.R., and Yakhshiboev S.S. 2023. Comparative results of surgical treatment of primary echinococcosis of the liver. *European Journal of Medical Genetics and Clinical Biology* 1 (2):36-45. <https://escience.net/index.php/JMGCB/article/view/223>

